

	Document:	Deliverable 8.3 - Production and distribution of CIRCPACK videos		
	Author:	ICLEI Europe	Version	1
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Deliverable 8.3

Production and
distribution of CIRCPACK
videos

CIRC-PACK - Towards circular economy
in the plastic packaging value chain

Grant agreement: 730423
From May 2017 to April 2020

Prepared by: Esben Pejstrup, ICLEI Europe
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DELIVERABLE FACTSHEET

Deliverable no.: 8.3
 Deliverable Name: Production and distribution of CIRCPACK videos
 Responsible Partner: ICLEI Europe
 WP no. and title: WP8, Awareness, dissemination, Communication
 Task no. and title: Task 8.2 Creation of dissemination materials
 Version: 1
 Version Date: 13/03/2020

Dissemination level	
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	PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the EC)
	RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the EC)
	CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the EC)

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The CIRC-PACK project has produced two videos in the project period to share with interested parties, both the general public and professionals working in the field, about the solutions developed. The first video was published in November 2018 to allow partners to share a simple presentation of the highly complex solutions. The second video was made available towards the end of the project, in March 2020, to support future communication and exploitation of the solutions. In addition, videos were also produced to present the results of the consumer tests carried out as part of Work Package 7.

The purpose of this deliverable is to provide an easily accessible overview of the videos, the reasoning behind them and how they have been disseminated.

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1 INTRODUCTION

The videos produced in CIRC-PACK as part of Deliverable 8.3 have been made to present the key solutions of the project to a wider public and the professional community working with circularity in plastics. Two main videos were produced and created by ICLEI in cooperation and in dialogue with work package leaders and the project coordinator CIRCE.

In the videos, the CIRC-PACK concept and demonstration activities were presented, with an emphasis on placing the activities in the larger context of the fight against plastic waste and European efforts to create a circular economy. All videos presented the information shared in an easy-to-understand language, appropriate for both a general audience and experts, to become acquainted with the project.

In addition, videos covering consumer approval of the CIRC-PACK solutions were produced by the CIRC-PACK partner OCU.

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2 VIDEOS

2.1 Links to videos

Video 1: "CIRC-PACK - from waste to resource": <https://youtu.be/jXUZzvyIhp8>

Picture 1: CIRC-PACK's introduction vide

Video 2: "CIRC-PACK final results": https://youtu.be/_Zt9UxsEnPc

Picture 2: CIRC-PACK final video

Videos Consumer tests:

- <https://youtu.be/eO8Doh4wFCg>
- <https://youtu.be/Vgk4wgljhJk>
- https://youtu.be/W7_TkGmTgMs (Spanish)
- <https://youtu.be/WexqWVvK1Hjw> (Spanish)
- <https://youtu.be/rvKAxXdKAF8> (Spanish)

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Picture 3: Example from consumer testing video

2.2 Content in videos

2.2.1 Video 1

The first CIRC-PACK video was produced in the fall of 2018 and presented the wide range of ambitions in CIRC-PACK in an easily understandable language avoiding scientific lexicon or references to technical terms only known by partners or people from the same working field. This was done to relate to a wider group of people who might be interested in the work performed in a European project to improve the recyclability of plastics.

The video was a total of 4:05 minutes long. Even if this length could be considered long for online use, this was chosen to provide the full picture of CIRC-PACK. In the first video, the content included:

- A global perspective;
- benefits of plastic;
- issues with fossil fuels in Plastic;
- the need for the CIRC-PACK solutions;
- Demo Case A, Demo Case B, Demo Case C;
- the partners and their expertise;
- a call to action;
- and the European objective of creating a Circular Economy.

The video was produced in a way which allowed for cutting it into shorter segments showcasing aspects of the entire video to various audiences. This was done in a version only focused on the three demo cases, which were also disseminated.

2.2.2 Video 2

The second video was produced leading up to the final CIRC-PACK event taking place on 17 March 2020. This video is 3:03 minutes long and is heavily focused on the three demo cases to present the main results of the project for a general audience. In addition, the video puts the CIRC-PACK solutions into the wider European perspective of the Circular Economy Action Plan (lasting from 2015 up to the European Green Deal 2020).

The video focuses on:

- The CIRC-PACK origin in the 2015 Action Plan;

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- Demo Case A results;
- Demo Case B results;
- Demo Case C results;
- European Green Deal

2.2.3 Videos, consumer tests

Videos were also produced by the partner OCU focusing on the testing of CIRC-PACK projects done with European consumers as part of work package 7. These videos included:

- OCU'S work in CIRC-PACK;
- CIRC-PACK general overview;
- Testing methodology;
- Some test results ;
- Link to all results.

2.3 Dissemination of videos

All videos were uploaded to Youtube on the channel of ICLEI Europe and shared through social media and by individual partners at events. In total, the first CIRC-PACK video has been watched almost 1.000 times on the Youtube platform (913 times until of 13/03/2020). In addition to this, a shorter version of the videos has been watched more than 500 times. The video was also included in CIRC-PACK newsletters and presented at different events.

The second official CIRC-PACK video was published on 17 March 2020 and will serve as a tool for interested parties to learn about CIRC-PACK's solutions even once the project is complete. The video will also feature prominently in the final period of the project and has been edited to allow for fitting with each individual demo case.

The videos on consumer testing from OCU has been watched More than 1.000 times on Youtube it total. The vidoes have also been used to disseminate work in other forums.

Picture 4: CIRC-PACK videos shared on Twitter

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3 CONCLUSIONS

The videos produced in CIRC-PACK were focused on the specific solutions in the wider context of European strategies and ambitions, and feed into a wider group of projects related to plastics and circular economy. The number of views, at the time being more than 2.500, indicates that the videos have been shared widely reaching a big audience.

It is expected that the videos will continue to have an impact after project's ending and will help remind the public about the work done in Europe to make the plastics industry circular through Horizon 2020.